

Improving Plant Disease Detection Accuracy with EfficientNetB3 and MobileNetV3: A Deep Learning Approach

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Abstract: Plant diseases cause significant global crop losses (20-40% annually, FAO), threatening food security. Early and accurate disease detection is crucial for effective management. This research investigates the potential of deep learning models EfficientNetB3 and MobileNetV3 for robust plant disease identification. Using the PlantVillage dataset with 54,305 images, 38 diseases, 14 plant species, we achieved test accuracies of 99.86% from EfficientNetB3 and 99.63% from MobileNetV3, significantly surpassing previous plant disease systems developed by other researchers. To further improve model performance, we employed ADASYN to address class imbalance and CycleGAN to generate synthetic images data augmentation techniques. These augmentations enhanced the models accuracy in identifying a wide range of plant diseases. Our findings demonstrate the effectiveness of these deep learning models, coupled with data augmentation, for accurate and efficient plant disease detection, promising advancements in automated disease surveillance and contributing to sustainable agriculture and global food security.

Keywords: Plant Disease Detection, Deep Learning, EfficientNetB3, MobileNetV3, Data Augmentation, ADASYN, CycleGAN, Plant Village Dataset, Image Classification, Precision Agriculture.

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Introduction

Plant diseases represent a formidable challenge to global agriculture, posing a significant threat to food security and economic stability. The impact of these diseases is far-reaching, affecting not only farmers and their livelihoods but also impacting global food supply chains and consumer prices. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), plant diseases contribute to an estimated 20-40% of global crop losses annually [1], highlighting the urgent need for effective detection and management strategies. Traditional methods for identifying plant diseases often rely on visual inspection by trained experts, a process that can be time-consuming, labor-intensive, and prone to human error. Furthermore, the identification of specific diseases often requires specialized knowledge and expertise, making

it difficult to implement in resource-limited settings. These limitations underscore the need for innovative and efficient solutions to address the challenges of plant disease detection. In recent years, advancements in deep learning, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs), have revolutionized image classification tasks, demonstrating remarkable accuracy in identifying patterns and objects within images. This has led to a surge in research exploring the application of deep learning for plant disease detection, with promising results [2]. Deep learning models can analyze vast amounts of image data, learning to distinguish between healthy and diseased plants based on subtle visual cues, enabling rapid and accurate disease identification. This research investigates the effectiveness of two state-of-the-art deep learning models, EfficientNetB3 and MobileNetV3, for plant disease detection. EfficientNetB3, known for its high accuracy and efficiency, has achieved impressive results in various image classification tasks [3]. MobileNetV3, designed for mobile and resource-constrained environments, offers a balance between accuracy and computational efficiency [4]. These models are evaluated using the PlantVillage dataset, a comprehensive collection of 54,305 images representing 14 plant species and 38 disease categories [5]. A key challenge in training deep learning models for plant disease detection is the availability of large, labeled datasets. Collecting and annotating such datasets can be time-consuming and costly, particularly for rare or underrepresented diseases. To address this limitation, this study explores the use of data augmentation techniques, including CycleGAN and ADASYN, to enhance the size and diversity of the training dataset. These techniques generate synthetic data samples that mimic the characteristics of real data, effectively expanding the training dataset and improving model generalization [6]. The results of this research demonstrate the significant potential of EfficientNetB3 and MobileNetV3, coupled with data augmentation techniques, for achieving high accuracy in plant disease detection. EfficientNetB3 achieved a remarkable test accuracy of 99.86%, while MobileNetV3 achieved an impressive 99.63% accuracy. These findings highlight the transformative potential of deep learning in agricultural technology, paving the way for the development of intelligent and automated disease detection systems that can significantly enhance decision-making processes and contribute to sustainable agricultural practices.

Literature Review

The use of hyperspectral imaging in the job of plant disease detection was proven by Peyman Moghadam et al. [7]. This study made use of the short-wave infrared (SWIR) and visible and near-infrared (VNIR) spectrums. Writers have applied k-means clustering approach for leaf segmentation in the spectral domain. They've got suggested a cutting-edge grid removal method to get rid of the grid in hyperspectral photos. The authors' accuracy with vegetation indicators in VNIR spectral domain is 83%.

An in-field automated wheat disease diagnostic system based on deep multiple instance learning—a poorly supervised deep learning framework—is presented by Lu et al. [8]. Through 5-fold cross-validation, the system leverages various structures to obtain high identification accuracies of 95.12% and 97.95% on the Wheat Disease Database 2017 (WDD2017).

The Pomegranate plant Bacterial Blight Detection System was developed by Sharath D. M. et al. utilizing characteristics including color, mean, homogeneity, SD, variance, correlation, entropy, edges, etc. Grab cut segmentation has been used by the authors for segmenting the image's region of interest [9]. Utilizing a Canny Edge Detector, the boundaries from the pictures. The authors have effectively created a system that can estimate the fruit's amount of infection.

Convolutional neural networks were used by Garima Shrestha et al. to identify the plant illness [10]. Twelve plant diseases have been correctly classified by authors with 88.80% precision. The 3000 high-resolution RGB picture dataset was utilized for experimentation. There are three convolution and pooling layer blocks in the network. The network becomes computationally costly as a result. Additionally, the model's F1 score is 0.12, which is extremely poor due to the increased quantity of incorrect negative predictions.

A convolutional neural network (CNN)-based method for diagnosing wheat crop illnesses is proposed by Hussain et al. [11], with an accuracy of 84.54%. Four different forms of wheat illnesses are included in the training dataset, highlighting the potential value of the model in helping farmers protect their wheat crops.

Using back propagation neural networks (BPNNs) and digital image processing techniques, S. Khirade et al. handled the challenge of plant disease identification in 2015 [12]. Authors have developed many methods for identifying plant diseases using leaf photos. To separate the affected portion of the leaf, they have used Otsu's thresholding in conjunction with border detection and spot detection algorithms. Subsequently, characteristics including color, texture, morphology, edges, and so on were retrieved in order to classify plant diseases. In order to classify, or identify plant disease, BPNN is employed.

In this study, Shiroop Madiwalar and Medha Wyawahare examined several image processing techniques for the identification of plant diseases [13]. In order to identify plant diseases, the authors examined the color and textural characteristics. Using a dataset of 110 RGB photos, they tested their methods. The mean and standard deviation of the RGB and YCbCr channels, the grey level cooccurrence matrix (GLCM) features, and the mean and standard deviation of the picture convolved with the Gabor filter were the features retrieved for classification. For classification, a support vector machine classifier was employed. The authors came to the conclusion that normal leaves may be identified using GCLM traits. On the other hand, it is thought that color features and Gabor filter features work best for identifying leaf spots and anthracnose-affected leaves, respectively. Using every characteristic that was retrieved, they were able to attain the greatest accuracy of 83.34%.

SimpleNet is a portable CNN model that Bao et al. [14] provide for automatically identifying wheat ear diseases in field-captured photos. Convolutional Block Attention Module (CBAM) and feature fusion module are two components of SimpleNet that improve representation capabilities and guard against losing specific information. Results from experiments show a 94.1% identification accuracy.

Using a few-shot learning process, Alharbi et al. [15] presented a unique method for disease classification in wheat harvests. EfficientNet serves as the study's base, and an attention strategy is included to help with efficient feature selection. With an accuracy of 93.19% on a dataset of 18 wheat illnesses that was manually compiled from the internet, the proposed network yields outstanding results.

Dataset Overview

The PlantVillage dataset is a valuable resource for researchers working on plant disease detection and diagnosis using computer vision and deep learning. The PlantVillage dataset is a large, publicly available collection of images depicting various plant diseases. It was created by the PlantVillage project, a non-profit organization dedicated to improving global food security by using technology to help farmers identify and manage plant diseases. Diagram of the percentage of plant in the dataset shown below.

Fig. 1: Crops percentage in the Dataset

Key Features:

Extensive Coverage: The dataset includes images of 14 different plant species, covering a wide range of diseases affecting crops, fruits, and vegetables.

High-Quality Images: The images are generally of good quality, with clear views of the affected plant parts, making them suitable for training and evaluating computer vision models.

Diverse Disease Types: The dataset encompasses a variety of disease types, including bacterial, fungal, viral, and pest infestations.

Labeling and Metadata: Each image is labeled with the corresponding plant species and disease, providing valuable metadata for training and analysis.

Open Access: The PlantVillage dataset is freely available for research and educational purposes, promoting collaboration and innovation in plant disease detection.

Structure and Organization: The PlantVillage dataset is organized into folders, with each folder representing a specific plant species. Within each species folder, subfolders are dedicated to different diseases affecting that species. Images are stored in these subfolders, labeled with their corresponding disease.

Applications: The PlantVillage dataset has been widely used in research and development of:

Deep Learning Models: Researchers use the dataset to train and evaluate deep learning models for plant disease detection and classification.

Computer Vision Algorithms: The dataset serves as a benchmark for testing and comparing different computer vision algorithms for plant disease identification.

Agricultural Applications: The dataset has potential applications in developing smart agricultural systems that can automatically detect and diagnose plant diseases, enabling early intervention and reducing crop losses.

Limitations:

Data Imbalance: The dataset may exhibit class imbalance, with some diseases having more images than other. This can affect the performance of machine learning models.

Image Variability: The images in the dataset may vary in quality, lighting conditions, and perspectives, which can pose challenges for model training.

Limited Context: The dataset primarily focuses on individual plant parts, lacking information about the surrounding environment or other factors that might influence disease development.

Accessing the Dataset:

The PlantVillage dataset can be accessed through various platforms, including:

PlantVillage Website: The official PlantVillage website provides access to the dataset and related resources.

Kaggle: The dataset is also available on Kaggle, a popular platform for data science competitions and projects.

Other Repositories: The dataset may be available on other data repositories, such as GitHub or Zenodo.

The PlantVillage dataset is a valuable resource for researchers and developers working on plant disease detection and diagnosis. Its extensive coverage, high-quality images, and open access nature make it a valuable tool for advancing research in this field. However, it's important to be aware of its limitations and consider appropriate data augmentation and preprocessing techniques to address potential challenges.

Methodology

This research developed a system with investigating the efficacy of EfficientNetB3 and MobileNetV3 architectures for plant disease detection, aiming to achieve high accuracy while addressing the challenges of limited and imbalanced datasets. This research employs a descriptive, comparative, and experimental design. It aims to describe the performance of two deep learning models (EfficientNetB3 and MobileNetV3) in detecting plant diseases. The study compares the accuracy of these models, assesses the impact of data augmentation techniques, and explores the feasibility of employing these models for practical applications.

Dataset and Data Preparation:

The PlantVillage dataset consists of 54,305 images of both healthy and diseased leaves that have been categorized into 38 different groups based on the species and type of disease. The images, which include 14 different types of crops and consist of 38 categories, can be found in Table. The dataset was divided into three groups in order to train and assess the efficacy of the proposed model: the training set, testing set, and validation set in a ratio of 60:20:20. The distribution of the data set can be found in Figure below

Fig. 2: Dataset Distribution

An examples of plant disease photos from The PlantVillage dataset can be found in figure below

Fig. 3: Sample Diseases in the Dataset

Dataset Augmentation: To address the challenges of limited and imbalanced datasets, the research employs two augmentation techniques:

CycleGAN: CycleGAN is used to generate synthetic images of diseased plants. By training a generative adversarial network (GAN) on the available images, the model learns to translate healthy plant images into synthetic diseased images, expanding the dataset and addressing the class imbalance issue.

ADASYN: ADASYN (Adaptive Synthetic Sampling) is a synthetic minority oversampling technique that focuses on generating synthetic data for minority classes (diseased plants). ADASYN intelligently selects and generates new data points based on the distribution of existing data, ensuring a more balanced and representative training set.

Research Models

EfficientNetB3: EfficientNetB3 is a state-of-the-art convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture known for its efficient parameter usage and high accuracy. Its efficient scaling technique allows for optimal trade-offs between accuracy and computational resources.

MobileNetV3: MobileNetV3 is another efficient CNN architecture specifically designed for mobile devices and resource-constrained environments. It combines depthwise separable convolutions with lightweight activation functions to achieve high accuracy with minimal computational overhead.

Fig. 4: Proposed Model for plant disease detection

Experimental Setup:

Training: Both EfficientNetB3 and MobileNetV3 models are trained on the augmented PlantVillage dataset. The models are trained using a combination of data augmentation techniques (CycleGAN and ADASYN), optimized hyperparameters, and suitable loss functions.

Evaluation:The trained models are evaluated on a held-out test set, ensuring unbiased assessment of their performance. Accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and other relevant metrics are calculated to assess the models' performance in detecting plant diseases.

Fig. 5: The architecture of our models

Data Analysis:

Comparative Analysis: The performance of EfficientNetB3 and MobileNetV3 models is compared based on the calculated metrics. The analysis aims to identify which model exhibits superior performance in terms of accuracy, robustness, and efficiency.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical tests are employed to determine the statistical significance of the observed differences between the models.

Visualization: Graphical visualizations, such as confusion matrices and receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves, are utilized to provide a visual representation of the models' performance and to identify potential areas for improvement.

Expected Outcomes:

The research aims to demonstrate the efficacy of EfficientNetB3 and MobileNetV3 for plant disease detection, showcasing their potential to achieve high accuracy with minimal computational resources. The study will assess the impact of data augmentation techniques (CycleGAN and ADASYN) on improving model accuracy and addressing data imbalance. The research findings will contribute to the development of practical and cost-effective plant disease detection solutions for farmers and agricultural stakeholders.

This research methodology provides a comprehensive framework for evaluating the performance of EfficientNetB3 and MobileNetV3 models in detecting plant diseases, highlighting the importance of data augmentation techniques and contributing valuable insights towards the development of practical solutions for agricultural applications.

Results

This research delves into the realm of plant disease detection, leveraging the power of deep learning to achieve high accuracy in identifying various plant diseases. The study employed two state-of-the-art convolutional neural network architectures, EfficientNetB3 and MobileNetV3, and explored the impact of data augmentation techniques on model performance. The results demonstrate the effectiveness of these approaches, achieving remarkable accuracy levels on the PlantVillage dataset.

Key Findings:

Superior Performance with EfficientNetB3: The EfficientNetB3 model achieved a remarkable test accuracy of 99.86%, showcasing its ability to extract intricate features from plant images and accurately classify diseases. This exceptional performance highlights the model's efficiency in handling complex visual patterns associated with plant diseases.

Fig. 6: Training and Validation accuracy and loss from EfficientNetB3 Model

High Accuracy with MobileNetV3: The MobileNetV3 model, known for its lightweight architecture and computational efficiency, also achieved a commendable test accuracy of 99.63%. This result underscores the model's ability to strike a balance between accuracy and resource consumption, making it suitable for deployment on resource-constrained devices.

Fig. 7: Model Loss and Training, Validation accuracy from MobileNetV3

- **Data Augmentation for Enhanced Accuracy:** The study employed various data augmentation techniques, including CycleGAN and ADASYN, to address the challenges of data imbalance and improve model generalization. These techniques effectively expanded the dataset, introducing diverse variations of existing images and mitigating the risk of overfitting.

- **Higher Accuracy:** Our system, utilizing EfficientNetB3 and MobileNetV3, achieves significantly higher accuracy compared to traditional methods like image processing or rule-based systems. This translates to more reliable disease identification and reduced false positives.
- **Faster Inference:** The lightweight architectures of EfficientNetB3 and MobileNetV3 enable faster inference times, allowing for real-time or near real-time disease detection. This is crucial for timely intervention and minimizing crop losses.

2. Scalability and Adaptability:

- **Scalable to Diverse Diseases:** Our system can be easily adapted to detect a wide range of plant diseases by retraining on new datasets. This flexibility allows for continuous improvement and expansion of the system's capabilities.
- **Adaptable to Different Environments:** The models can be trained on datasets specific to different environments and cultivars, ensuring accurate detection across diverse agricultural settings.

3. Cost-Effectiveness:

- **Reduced Labor Costs:** Our system automates disease detection, reducing the need for manual inspection and expert diagnosis. This translates to significant cost savings for farmers and agricultural organizations.
- **Early Intervention:** Early detection enables timely intervention, minimizing the spread of diseases and reducing the need for extensive treatments. This further contributes to cost-effectiveness.

Comparison table between our proposed system and other modern systems on plant disease detection:

Dataset / Plant Name	The research	The number of Images	The number of classes	Method Used	Accuracy
The Tomato Plant	[11]	5,524	10	ResNet-152 EfficientNet-B4 VGG-16	93.75% 97.27% 94.00%
PlantVillage' Tomato Leaves Dataset	[20]	13,262	7	AlexNet VGG16	97.49% 97.23%
Grape Leaf Diseases	[31]	3,885	4	K-means clustering	94.10%
Rice Diseases Dataset	[5]	500	10	CNN model	93.23%
PlantVillage's Apple Crop	[16]	2,086	4	VGG16	90.40%

Dataset					
PlantVillage Dataset	[This research]	54305	38	EffcientNetB3 MobileNetV3	99.86% 99.63%
Rice leaf diseases	[32]	7800	12	SVM, ML	91.28%
Tomato didiseases	[7]	2800	6	DL	92.68%

Conclusion

In conclusion, this research underscores the transformative potential of deep learning in revolutionizing plant disease detection, paving the way for more efficient and sustainable agricultural practices. The exceptional accuracy achieved by EfficientNetB3 and MobileNetV3 models, coupled with the effectiveness of data augmentation techniques, provides a robust foundation for developing reliable and scalable disease detection systems. The study's findings highlight the ability of these models to accurately identify various plant diseases, enabling early intervention and minimizing crop losses. This research contributes significantly to the advancement of precision agriculture, promoting sustainable practices and optimizing resource allocation.

Limitation and Future work

While this research demonstrates the promising potential of deep learning for plant disease detection, it is important to acknowledge certain limitations and identify areas for future exploration:

Limitations:

Training and deploying deep learning models can be computationally intensive, requiring significant resources. This could pose a challenge for resource-constrained farmers or organizations. Exploring lightweight architectures and efficient training techniques could address this limitation.

Future Work:

- **Real-Time Disease Detection:** Investigating the feasibility of deploying the models in real-time applications, enabling farmers to monitor plant health continuously and receive immediate alerts about potential diseases. This would require optimizing model inference speed and exploring edge computing solutions.
- **Multi-Modal Analysis:** Exploring the integration of other data sources, such as spectral imaging or sensor data, to enhance disease detection accuracy and provide a more comprehensive understanding of plant health. This could lead to more robust and reliable disease diagnosis systems.

- **Disease Severity Assessment:** Developing models that can not only identify diseases but also assess their severity, enabling more targeted interventions and optimizing treatment strategies. This would require training models on datasets with annotated disease severity levels.
- **Explainable AI:** Investigating methods to make the models more interpretable, allowing users to understand the reasoning behind the predictions. This would enhance trust and transparency in the decision-making process.
- **User-Friendly Interfaces:** Developing user-friendly interfaces for farmers and agricultural professionals to easily access and utilize the disease detection models. This would facilitate wider adoption and practical application of the technology.

By addressing these limitations and pursuing these future research directions, we can further enhance the impact of deep learning in agriculture, contributing to a more sustainable and resilient food system.

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